

Green Energy Based Smart Farming System for Rural Living hood using Arduino

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Abstract—It is primarily about the improvement of current greenhouse farming practices by using Arduino technology for better yield. This project aim is to develop an automated plant watering and soil quality testing system. The main purpose behind this system is to maintain the proper pH level of soil, conserve the wastage of water, and maintain suitable atmosphere inside the greenhouse farming system. Apart from these, it reduces farmer's labor, effort, and wrong treatment for plants due to their negligence. It uses pH sensor to measure the soil's acidity & basicity property. The pH level should be maintained by this device. When the pH content of the soil goes below a standard value for a plant, the pump system is triggered on and the soil is watered with limewater. The soil of the plants is watered efficiently till the desired value is reached and the pump is switched off automatically & also when the pH content is above from the standard value of pH then it spread organic fertilizer. It works on solar power so, here we are using solar panels to provide solar power to the system and charge the batteries to operate at night. It uses soil moisture sensors to measure the level of moisture present in the soil. When the moisture level of the soil goes below a standard value, pump system will get triggered and the plants are watered until the moisture of the soil reaches the standard value, the pump is turned off automatically. Apart from this, we are using LDR sensor to maintain proper light energy for plant's growth. The temperature and humidity sensor are also provided with an appropriate weather inside the greenhouse farming. For providing plants safety purpose the ultrasonic sensor is used in this system. All the information is shown in the LCD display and the microcontroller takes necessary actions.

Index Terms— Arduino, Moisture Indicator, Moisture Sensor, pH Sensor, Solar Panel, Water Pump.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE source of fossil fuels gets continuously reduced and main concern over environmental pollution; have forced ourselves to explore new non-conventional energy sources. The renewable resources such as solar energy, control the increasing demand for energy and reducing the pollution level of the environment. India's climate is considered as a hot tropical country except some states. The availability of sunlight in India over a year is good. Therefore, we are using it for various purposes and it is a positive idea. India is an agriculture based country. Agriculture in India is still carried out in conventional way and lags behind in integrating modern technologies. Around 55 percent of Indian population has been engaged in agriculture and allied activities which constitute only 15 percent of GDP so it becomes much important for the stakeholders involved to come out of the conventional agricultural practices and modernized the agriculture using technology [5]. The economic contribution of agriculture to India's GDP is steadily

declining with the country's broad-based economic growth while large number of people continues to work in agricultural sector. Hence, there is an immediate need to improve the system, which can increase the yield and produce healthy organic food. So greenhouse farming is the solution for the improvement of the farm output. Mainly, greenhouse is a glass house whose interior's temperature increases when exposed to sunlight. Therefore, while the weather may be cold outside temperature is remaining friendly and warm for the plants growing inside the greenhouse. Different plants require different amount of moisture, humidity, temperature, and light wavelength, and lack of awareness of this information or negligence of a person cultivating land can cause plants to die before maturing. As well as the output of the farm becomes decreased. This solar powered based smart greenhouse farming system [6] not only solves these problems but also provides a pollution free source of energy [4].

I. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In this solar powered smart farming system [1], we used different type of sensors and components as mentioned below.

- Temperature sensor : It is an electronic device which helps to measure temperature of environment around its and convert these input data into an electrical signal. Temperature sensor can measure.
- Humidity sensor : It is an electronic device which sense and measure moisture as well as temperature of air. We can monitor humidity and temperature by using DHT11 or DHT22 with Arduino.
- Moisture sensor : It helps us to measure volumetric water content in the soil.
- pH sensor : It is an equipment which is used to detect basicity or acidity of any solution.
- Ultrasonic sensor : It is an electronic device which measure distance of a target object by emitting ultrasonic wave and converts the reflected wave into an electrical signal. Main components of ultrasonic sensor is transmitter and receiver.
- LDR sensor : LDR is a light dependent resistor. When light rays drop on it, resistance will change immediately. In bright light resistor of LDR is increased in order of megaohms but in darkness resistance value is dropped to order of hundred ohms.
- Solar panel : Solar panel is a device which converts sunlight into electricity.
- Battery : It is a device that converts chemical energy into electrical energy by means of redox reaction.

We can also control the proper atmosphere inside the greenhouse by using this system. In this system, we are using different types of sensors. These sensors are used to tackle and solve different types of problems in the greenhouse. Arduino microcontroller does the whole work.

I. PROPOSED IMPLEMENTATION OF GREENHOUSE FARMING SYSTEM

Figures 1-5 describe the basic flow of the work and they show how various sensors work in the given system. Here Arduino microcontroller is working as the main CPU of the system [3]. It takes the inputs from the sensors and then controls different outputs and parameters as shown in the flow charts.

Fig. 1. LDR sensor

Fig. 2. Ultrasonic Sensor.

Fig. 3. Moisture and Temperature Control of Air

Fig. 4. Humidity Sensor of Soil

Fig. 5. pH Sensor.

Fig. 1 describes how the LDR sensor works and Fig. 2 shows how Ultrasonic sensor works. Fig. 3 shows how the moisture and temperature of air can be controlled. Fig. 4 shows how soil humidity sensor works and Fig. 5 describes how the pH sensor works.

II. HARDWARE IMPLEMENTATION OF GREENHOUSE FARMING SYSTEM

At first, data has been collected from the five sensors LDR sensor, ultrasonic sensor, humidity sensor, soil moisture sensor and pH sensor. Then the measured information has been sent to Arduino UNO. The Arduino takes necessary decision or actions, and displays the sensors values to the farmers. The Arduino also starts necessary action to prevent the problem. Following subsections describe how the sensors work [2].

A. Soil Humidity Sensor

In this modern daily life, we can easily measure the humidity of soil, by using a microcontroller and electronic sensor. In this system, the Arduino microcontroller and soil moisture (EC-28) sensor are used. The soil moisture sensor has two parts, signal converter and sensing probe.

The sensor probe has two pins ('+' pin & '-' pin). The signal converter has six pins. One side of signal converter has two input pins ('+' & '-'), the other side of the signal converter has four output pins like vcc, analog output, digital output, GND.

At the time of measuring the moisture of the soil, first the terminal of the sensing probe is connected to the signal converter's input pins. Now the rest of the four pins of the signal converter are connected to the microcontroller. In this case, the given input signal of the microcontroller is analog input data and this analog input, data will be sent through the analog output pin of the signal converter. When the sensor value is greater than the threshold value then the microcontroller sends the digital signal to the relay module. Then the relay module switches on the water pump and water starts flowing.

In addition, the values are displayed in LCD display. At every instant the sensor senses the serial analog input and then sends it to the microcontroller. When the value of the sensor value reaches the equal or lesser than the threshold value, then the microcontroller sends the signal to the relay. Then the relay stops the water pump.

B. Temperature and humidity sensor

Here in this system, we also find the ambient temperature and humidity of the air and we can control the ambient humidity and temperature of the greenhouse. The ambient temperature and humidity is very crucial for the growth of the plants inside the greenhouse. Here in this greenhouse system we mainly use DHT-11 or DHT-22 as temperature and humidity sensor. DHT22 is the more expensive, which obviously has better specifications. Its temperature measuring range is from -40°C to +125°C with +-0.5 degrees accuracy, while with DHT11 temperature range is from 0°C to 50°C with +-2 degrees accuracy. However, DHT22 is more precise, more accurate and works in a bigger range of temperature and humidity. These sensors help us measure the exact value of the temperature and humidity of the air. DHT-11 sensor has four pins. Those are Vcc, Data, No connection and GND, respectively. If we are using DHT-22 sensor module then it has three pins, viz., Vcc, Data and Ground. These two sensors' output is digital. Relative humidity and temperature are sensed by this sensor. It uses a capacitive humidity sensor and a thermistor to measure respectively the humidity and

temperature of the air inside the greenhouse system. The measured data is sent through the data pin to the microcontroller as a digital signal. If the sensor value is greater than the threshold value of the sensor then the microcontroller gives a signal to the relay. Now the relay starts the fan and water spreading motor. When the temperature and humidity of air reach its desired values then microcontroller stops the water spreading motor and fan automatically.

C. *LDR Sensor*

In this system, we can also control the adequate light to enhance the growth of the plants inside the greenhouse. We know that the main ingredient of the photosynthesis process is the light. When a plant gets proper light energy during a day then growth of the plant is enhance. In a normal day, a plant takes light from environment approximately 12- 13 hours. Here we are using the LDR sensor during cloudy and night time when the adequate light is not present in the environment. The LDR sensor will turn on the light automatically. LDR is a light dependent resistor, which can detect the intensity of light energy. It is associated with both the analog output pin (A0) and digital output pin (D0) respectively on the board. When the light intensity is high at that moment the resistance of the LDR becomes low. If the light intensity is low then the resistance of the LDR becomes higher. The sensor module has a potentiometer that can be adjusted to change the sensitivity of LDR towards the light. This module has four pins such as

- Vcc
- GND
- Analog output
- Digital output.

The input voltage of this LDR sensor module is D.C. (3.3v to 5v). By using this sensor module, we can easily measure the analog and digital value of the resistance in this system. The lower intensity of light increases the resistance of the LDR sensor module. When the value of the LDR resistance crosses the threshold value of the resistance, then the sensor sends a signal to the microcontroller. Then the microcontroller sends a signal to the relay module and the relay module turns on light. When the resistance value becomes lower than the threshold value, then light is turned off automatically.

D. *Ultrasonic Sensor*

In this system, we can also detect any harmful insects or living organisms. Here we are using the ultrasonic sensor (HC-SR04) to protect plants inside the greenhouse system. Ultrasonic transducers or ultrasonic sensors are a type of acoustic sensor divided into three board categories. Those are respectively

- Transmitter
- Receivers
- Transceivers.

Transmitters convert the electrical signal into ultrasound. Receivers convert the ultrasonic sound into electrical signals. Transceivers can both transmit and receive the ultrasound. The Ultrasonic Distance Sensor can report the range of objects up to 13 feet away. This ultrasonic sensor (HC-SR04) consists of two ultrasonic transducers. One acts as a transmitter, which converts electrical signal into 40 KHz ultrasonic sound pulses and the receiver, listens for the transmitted pulses.

Its non-contact detection range is between 2 cm to 400 cm (that is about an inch to 13 feet) with an accuracy of 3mm. This sensor module has four pins such as V_{CC}, trigger pin, echo and GND. The sensor sends a signal to the microcontroller then the microcontroller sends the output data on LCD display.

E. pH Sensor

In this system, we are also able to measure the amount of alkalinity and acidity in soil. The pH sensor module has two main parts, one is known as pH probe and another one is pH sensor interface circuit. The pH sensor interface circuit has right no. of pins like

- PGND
- PRB
- TX
- RX
- VCC
- Analog Output
- Digital output.

The standard pH scale is represented by a value that can range from 0-14. It is a very important factor of a soil. If the pH value of the soil is very low or high then the plants' growth is affected. So we have to maintain the right pH value of the soil. By using this sensor, we can measure the pH value of soil to determine the suitable soil for farming. The pH probe has two terminals, one is positive and another one is negative. Now, the two terminals are dipped in the solution of soil to measure the pH level. If the H⁺ ions' majority is observed in that solution the solution is acidic. The terminals of the probes act as a battery. Then it can produce a greater voltage. The pH meter takes advantage of this and acts a voltmeter. It measures the voltage difference of the soil solution and a known solution. This voltage difference is used to deduce the difference in pH value and also measure the pH value. The microcontroller shows this value in the display and also takes necessary actions for it.

F. Block Diagram of the Implementation

The supply power of this system is solar energy. That's why this system is pollution free system. The whole work is done by the microcontroller UNO. The microcontroller's input is given by these sensors and signal conditioning units as shown in Fig. 6.

Fig. 6. Block diagram

Fig. 7. Circuit diagram of the implementation.

Fig. 8. Circuit diagram pH sensor with Arduino UNO.

V. CONCLUSION

Arduino based greenhouse farming system is technically modern and very efficient for farmer and common people. This implementation has shown that it is possible to produce all kinds of vegetables or plants easily with the help of this technology. Different types of environmental conditions can be explained at the same time with different parameters, as a result of which the farmers involved in agriculture and get huge benefits. This system provides more or less accurate information about the humidity, moisture of soil, atmospheric temperature, adequate light, pH factor of soil and detect any malicious activity near the tree. The system is reliable and it can be installed anywhere in the greenhouse, even on farm land. The beneficial aspects of this implementation are that, it takes less time to cultivate, costs less, reduces water wastage and increases grain quality with minimum effort. As a result of such facilities, the quality of life in those area can be improved.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. R. Pasha, and B. Yogesha, "Microcontroller Based Automatic Irrigation System," International Journal of Engineering and Science (IJES), Hassan, vol. 3, pp. 6-9, July 2014.
- [2] B. S. Dhanne, S. Kedare, and S. S. Dhanne, "Modern Solar Power Irrigation System by using ARM," International Journal of Research in Engineering and Technology (IJRET), vol. 3, pp. 20-25, May 2014.
- [3] M. Usha Rani, and S. Kamalesh, "Web Based Service to Monitor Automatic Irrigation System for the Agriculture Field Using Sensors," International Conference on Advances in Electrical Engineering (ICAEE- 2014), Vellore, India, pp. 1-5, January 9-11, 2014.
- [4] C. C. Baseca, S. Sendra, J. Lloret, and J. Tomas, "A Smart Decision System for Digital Farming," Agronomy, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 216:1-19, 2019.
- [5] Ministry of External Affairs (2015), "India in Business," Investment and Technology Promotion Division, Govt. of India.
- [6] A. I. Okunola, "Glasshouse Production of Vegetable and Ornamentals for Agricultural Production in Nigeria," World Science Research Journals, vol. 1, no. 3, pp. 113-119, 2013.

